

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

This research paper aims at investigating the level of emotional intelligence of physical education teachers and the variables associated with their emotional intelligence. The data used in the study is primary in nature which has been collected through issue of structured questionnaire in both Tamil and English language. A sample of 253 physical education teachers working in Coimbatore district has been selected through Snowball sampling technique. Simple percentage analysis, ANOVA, ‘t’ test and chi-square test are applied in analyzing the data. The study discloses that physical education teachers working with high grade designation, more number of working hours per day, high experience in the previous institution have the ability to balance their level of emotions.

Key Words: Emotional intelligence – Physical Education Teachers.

Introduction:

A growing number of studies have suggested that teachers' personal competencies and more specifically Emotional Intelligence (EI) are particularly important for teacher effectiveness. Emotional intelligence refers to ability of individuals to identify their own emotions and those of others discern between different feelings and label them appropriately, use emotional information to guide thinking and behavior, and manage and/or adjust emotions to adapt to environments or achieve one's goals. Emotional Intelligence includes traits like self-awareness, social deftness, the ability to delay gratification, to be optimistic in the face of adversity, to channel strong emotions and to show empathy towards others. Goleman (1995) identifies the five elements as the components of emotional intelligence: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills. Study conducted by Singh (2003) found that teachers need to be high in their emotional intelligence to be successful. Sutton and Wheatly (2003) highlighted that emotional competence of teachers is necessary both in general for their own well-being and for effectiveness and quality in carrying out teaching learning process in the classroom and in particular for the socio-emotional development of the students.

Review of Literature:

Jaya Amantha Kumar and Balakrishnan Muniandy (2012) in their study find that emotional intelligence improves with age and experience, which shows that growth of emotional intelligence increases with maturity. Amit Kauts and Vijay Kumar (2013) in their study reveal that teachers with low emotional intelligence experienced more occupational stress than teachers with high emotional intelligence. Sudhamayi (2013) in her study discloses that there exists a significant negative correlation between emotional intelligence and personal strain. Turkey Nuri Tok and Sukran Tok and Sevda Dogan Dolapcioglu (2013) in their study find that emotional intelligence significantly predicts student-centered classroom management. Also, they disclose that there exists a positive and significant relationship between primary school teachers' level of emotional intelligence and student-centered classroom management approaches. Pravin Laxman Kothawade (2014) in his study exposes that the emotional intelligence of higher secondary school teachers is high and majority of them are satisfied in their job. Also, he observes that there exists a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of higher secondary school teachers. Sarvamangala (2015) in his study shows that secondary school teachers who possess high emotional quotient are high in their attitude towards teaching profession, students, social work and professional growth. Also, she reveals that identification of the area of emotional intelligence and teacher attitude might help the secondary school teachers to exploit their classroom activities and their personal life.

Statement of the Problem:

Physical education (PE) teachers are occupying a strong position in all organization including teaching and non-teaching, as they are preparing the students by not only the theoretical method, but also physically and mentally. Their daily work is exercising to fitness them and motivating students physically through giving some exercise physically or mentally. Further, it is observed that physical education teachers have to mentally balance with two factors namely, *external factors* which are institutional environment, family situation, political issues and management and other side is *internal factors* which include personal behaviour, self emotions, etc. so their work involvement depends upon their emotions. Thus, emotions play a vital role to determine the job involvement of physical education

teachers. This raises the following questions: What is their level of emotional intelligence? What are the variables that influence their level of emotional intelligence?

Objectives of the Study:

- To identify mean difference between / among the select variables and emotional intelligence of physical education teachers
- To ascertain the association between the select variables and their level of emotional intelligence

Research Methodology:

The study is mainly based on primary data and the data required for the study have been collected through issue of structured questionnaire which is prepared both in Tamil and English language. The questionnaire contains questions relating to the personal profile, occupational details and emotional intelligence (Goleman's scale) of physical education teachers. A sample of 253 physical education teachers working in Colleges and Universities in Coimbatore district have been selected by adopting snowball sampling technique. The statistical tools like ANOVA, 't' test and Chi-square test are used to analyse the data.

Findings of the Study:

The findings of the study is divided into three sections namely, socio-economic profile of sample physical educational teachers, occupational details and emotional intelligence of physical education teachers.

i) Socio-Economic Profile:

- Majority of 150 (59.29%) teachers are residing in rural area
- Most of the teachers i.e. 120 (49.43%) belong to the age between 30 and 40 years
- Majority i.e. 185 (73.12%) teachers are male
- Majority of 199 (78.66%) teachers are married
- Most of the 98 (38.74%) teachers' educational qualification is Ph.D
- Majority of the teachers i.e. 222(87.75%) have not cleared the NET/SET exam
- Majority of 171(67.59%) teachers belong to nuclear family
- Majority of 147(58.10%) teachers are the head in their family
- Majority i.e. 163(64.43%) teachers have two earning members in their family
- Majority of the teachers, 133 (52.57%) have above two non-earning members in their family
- Most of the 106 (41.90%) teachers have up to three members in their family
- Most of the teachers i.e. 97 (38.33%) earnings per month is between Rs.10,001 and Rs. 25,000
- Most of the 112 (44.27%) teachers' family income per month is between Rs.25,001 and Rs.50,000
- Most of the teachers i.e. 109 (43.08%) family expenditure per month is between Rs.10,001 and Rs.20,000

ii) Occupational Details:

- Majority of the teachers, 218 (86.17%) are working in colleges
- Majority i.e. 187 (73.91%) teachers are working in urban based institution
- Majority of 153 (60.47%) teachers are directors
- Majority i.e. 171(67.59%) teachers' nature of employment is temporary
- Majority of 200 (79.05%) teachers are working from 8 to 10 hours per day
- Most of the 105 (41.51%) teachers have 5 to 10 years of experience in the present institution
- Most i.e. 86 (33.99%) teachers have less than two years of experience in the previous institution
- Majority of 134 (52.96%) teachers have less than ten years of total experience in their job
- Majority i.e. 138 (54.55%) teachers are travelling 10 to 20 kilometers distance from their home to work place
- Most of the 115(45.45%) teachers are coming by two wheeler

(iii) Emotional Intelligence of Physical Education Teachers:

This section deals with the computation of level of emotional intelligence, variables considered for measuring level of emotional intelligence and findings relating to the emotional intelligence of physical education teachers based on ANOVA, 't' test and Chi-square test.

a) Level of Emotional Intelligence: Emotional intelligence on physical education teachers has been measured by giving scores to emotional intelligence related questions. Ninety-nine such questions are included in the questionnaire. Answers the questions have been rated on six-point scale. Thus, the maximum score a physical education teacher would get is 594. Scores obtained by each physical education teacher is divided by 594 and multiplied by 100 to convert into an index. This index is termed as 'emotional intelligence index'. The level of emotional intelligence thus calculated ranges between 32.15 and 95.12 and the grand mean of emotional intelligence index is 73.67. Of the 253 physical education teachers, 138 (54.55%) are with emotional intelligence index above the average and 115 (45.45%) are with emotional intelligence indices below the average. Based on the emotional intelligence index, the physical education teachers are divided into three groups as physical education teachers with low, medium and high level of emotional intelligence. In order to classify the physical education teachers into three such groups, quartiles have been made use of. Accordingly, physical education teachers with emotional intelligence index ranging up to 63.69 are termed as physical education teachers with low level of emotional intelligence; those with emotional intelligence index between 63.70 and 83.64 are termed as physical education teachers with medium level of emotional intelligence and those physical education teachers with emotional intelligence index above 83.64

are termed as physical education teachers with high level of emotional intelligence. Of the 253 physical education teachers, 29 (11.46%) have low level of emotional intelligence; 187 (73.91%) have medium level of emotional intelligence and the remaining 37 (14.62%) have high level of emotional intelligence.

b) Variables considered for Level of Emotional Intelligence: Twenty four variables namely area of residence, age, gender, marital status, educational qualifications, qualified with NET/SET, type of family, status in the family, number of earning members in the family, number of non-earning members in the family, size of the family, monthly income, family income per month, family expenditure per month, type of institution, location of institution, designation, nature of employment, number of working hours per day, year of experience in the present institution, year of experience in the previous institution, total experience, distance between home and workplace and mode of transport have been selected in order to test whether the observation on level of emotional intelligence differs based on these variables and if there really exists any association between each of the variables and level of emotional intelligence. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and ‘t’ test have been made use to study differences in mean value and level of emotional intelligence and chi-square test have been employed to examine association between the variables and level of emotional intelligence. Levels of significance chosen are one and five per cent level.

c) Select Variables and Emotional Intelligence - ANOVA and ‘t’ Test: To test the mean difference between / among the select variables and emotional intelligence of physical education teachers, the ANOVA and ‘t’ test has been applied.

H₀: There is no mean difference between the select variables and level of emotional intelligence.

Table 1: Select Variables and Emotional Intelligence – ANOVA and ‘t’ Test

S.No	Variables	d.f. (V ₁ , V ₂)	Calculate d F & ‘t’ Value	Table Value (F & ‘t’)		Result
				At 5%	At 1%	
1	Area of Residence	2, 250	1.217	3.031	4.691	Not Significant
2	Age	2, 250	0.417	3.031	4.691	Not Significant
3	Gender	251	2.403*	1.969	2.596	Significant
4	Marital Status	251	0.231	1.969	2.596	Not Significant
5	Educational qualification	3, 249	0.128	2.641	3.861	Not Significant
6	Qualified with NET / SET	251	0.954	1.969	2.596	Not Significant
7	Type of family	251	0.235	1.969	2.596	Not Significant
8	Status in the family	251	0.799	1.969	2.596	Not Significant
9	No. of earning members in the family	2, 250	1.728	3.031	4.691	Not Significant
10	No. of non-earning members in the family	2, 250	0.881	3.031	4.691	Not Significant
11	Total no. of members in the family	2, 250	0.663	3.031	4.691	Not Significant
12	Monthly income	4, 248	0.335	2.408	3.396	Not Significant
13	Family income per month	4, 248	0.702	2.408	3.396	Not Significant
14	Family expenditure per month	4, 248	1.610	2.408	3.396	Not Significant
15	Type of institution	251	1.960	1.969	2.596	Not Significant
16	Location of institution	2, 250	0.389	3.031	4.691	Not Significant
17	Designation	5, 247	3.278**	2.251	3.092	Highly Significant
18	Nature of employment	251	1.222	1.969	2.596	Not Significant
19	Number of working hours per day	2, 250	8.713**	3.031	4.691	Highly Significant
20	Year of experience - Present institution	2, 250	0.065	3.031	4.691	Not Significant
21	Year of experience - Previous institution	2, 250	3.750*	3.031	4.691	Significant
22	Total experience	2, 250	1.978	3.031	4.691	Not Significant
23	Distance between home and workplace	2, 250	0.117	3.031	4.691	Not Significant
24	Mode of transport	4, 248	0.802	2.408	3.396	Not Significant

The table above shows that out of the twenty-four variables selected for testing the mean difference with emotional intelligence of physical education teachers, three variables are found to be significant. Of them, two variables namely designation and number of working hours per day is found to have highly significant difference at one per cent level whereas gender and year of experience in the previous institution are found to have significant difference with emotional intelligence of physical education teachers at five per cent level.

d) Select Variables and Level of Emotional Intelligence – Chi-Square Test: To examine the association between the select variables and emotional intelligence of physical education teachers, the Chi-square test has been employed.

H₀: There is no association between the select variables and level of emotional intelligence

Table 2: Select Variables and Level of Emotional Intelligence – Chi-Square Test

S.No	Variables	d.f.	Calculated χ^2 Value	Table Value		Result
				At 5 %	At 1%	
1	Area of residence	4	4.931	9.488	13.277	Not Significant
2	Age	4	3.752	9.488	13.277	Not Significant
3	Gender	2	6.937	5.991	9.210	Significant
4	Marital status	2	2.884	5.991	9.210	Not Significant
5	Educational qualification	6	3.820	12.592	16.812	Not Significant
6	Passed NET/SET	2	2.397	5.991	9.210	Not Significant

S.No	Variables	d.f.	Calculated χ^2 Value	Table Value		Result
				At 5 %	At 1%	
7	Type of family	2	0.467	5.991	9.210	Not Significant
8	Status in the family	2	3.461	5.991	9.210	Not Significant
9	Number of Earning members	4	3.678	9.488	13.277	Not Significant
10	Number of Non-Earning members	4	7.472	9.488	13.277	Not Significant
11	Size of the Family	4	4.540	9.488	13.277	Not Significant
12	Monthly income of individual	8	1.723	15.507	20.090	Not Significant
13	Family income	8	13.597	15.507	20.090	Not Significant
14	Family expenditure	8	10.144	15.507	20.090	Not Significant
15	Type of institution	2	3.484	5.991	9.210	Not Significant
16	Location of institution	4	2.594	9.488	13.277	Not Significant
17	Designation	10	17.129	18.307	23.209	Not Significant
18	Nature of employment	2	1.231	5.991	9.210	Not Significant
19	Number of working hours	4	17.917	9.488	13.277	Significant
20	Year of experience - Present institution	4	4.855	9.488	13.277	Not Significant
21	Year of experience - Previous institution	4	9.502	9.488	13.277	Significant
22	Total Experience	4	14.522	9.488	13.277	Significant
23	Distance between home and workplace	4	1.292	9.488	13.277	Not Significant
24	Mode of transport	8	7.302	15.507	20.090	Not Significant

The table above shows that out of 24 variables, four variables are found to be significant. Of them, number of working hours per day and total experience are found to be significant at one per cent level whereas gender and year of experience in the previous institution are found to be significant at five per cent level.

Conclusion:

The present study focuses on level of emotional intelligence of physical education teachers working in Coimbatore district. It reveals that gender, designation, number of working hours per day and year of experience in the previous institution are found to be significant. Therefore, the physical education teachers who are working with high grade designation, more working hours per day and more experience in the previous institution are exceedingly balanced their level of emotions in their work place. Hence, the Government and the Institution may try to recognize the experienced and hard working physical education teachers by understanding the nature and significance of physical education department in shaping the students minds and physique.

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